

Chemical Reactions in Infra-red Radiations. Part II.

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In a recent communication (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 451) we have shown that several chemical changes can be accelerated by radiations of mean wave-length $7304\text{\AA}$. In this paper we are recording our results on the acceleration of some other reactions by radiations of the same mean wave-length and wave-lengths longer than $7304\text{\AA}$.

Some years ago Wood ("Physical Optics," 1911, p. 15) stated that a light filter consisting of a saturated solution of potassium dichromate placed in a cobalt-glass cell of one centimetre thickness cuts off all radiations shorter than $6900\text{\AA}$. Ellis and Wells ("Chemical Action of Ultra-violet Rays," 1925, p. 80) state that the same filter only transmits infra-red rays of wave-lengths longer than $10140\text{\AA}$.

By using a copper arc and a photographic plate sensitised by neocyanin, we have observed that the above filter cuts off all radiations

shorter than $8000\text{\AA}$. It will be seen in the above photograph that the copper line $8000\text{\AA}$ is partially transmitted by a saturated

solution of potassium dichromate placed in a cobalt-glass cell of one centimetre thickness. Anti-screen photographic plates were sensitised by dipping in a bath containing the following substances:—

Water alcohol mixture (85 : 80) = 150 c.c. + neocyanin solution (1 : 2000 in C_2H_5OH) = 1.5 c.c. + kryptocyanin solution (1 : 1000 in C_2H_5OH) = 2 c.c. + dicyanin solution (1 : 100 in C_2H_5OH) 2.5 c.c. + conc. NH_4OH = 5.5 c.c.

The plate was soaked for 5 minutes in the above bath and rinsed for $\frac{1}{2}$ minute in alcohol and was rapidly dried.

Moreover by using a Nutting's spectrophotometer, we have been able to make sure that the same filter can completely cut off all visible radiations.

We have measured the velocity of sixteen chemical reactions in radiations from a 1000-watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp filtered by the dichromate and cobalt glass filter. It appears that the mean wave-length of radiation transmitted by this filter is 8500 Å.

The experimental arrangement was the same as described in the previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 451).

The experimental results are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Hydrazine Hydrochloride and Iodine at 25°.

N/5-Hydrazine hydrochloride = 5 c.c. *N*/100-Iodine = 10 c.c.

1.25*N*-Hydrochloric acid = 5 c.c.

Region $\lambda = 8500\text{Å}$.

Time in minutes ...	0	20	40	60	70
Thiosulphate per 3 c.c. of the reacting mixture ...	6.8	5.35	4.2	3.9	2.9 c.c.
k_1 (Unimolecular) ...	—	0.00522	0.00523	0.00523	

Mean 0.00523

Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in the dark, k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}$, k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$, k_1	Temperature coefficient (dark).	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction.		Quantum yield.	
					$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}$.	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$.	$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}$.	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$.
25°	0.00486	0.00589	0.00523				4	2
35°	0.0121	0.0148	0.0134	2.60	2.18	2.24	7.4	3.6
45°	0.0302	0.0358	0.0330	2.50	2.03	2.15	9.6	4.9

Calculation of Quantum Yield.

The dimension of the observation cell is (3 cm.)³ internally. The energy per quantum (corresponding to $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$) = 2.3×10^{-12} ergs.

The radiomicrometer was calibrated for the amount of energy absorbed to produce 1 mm. deflection on the scale by using a Hefner lamp under standard conditions. This value of the energy was found to be 2.85 ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

	Deflection (cm.).	Difference in deflection (cm.).
Distilled water	... 22.6	
Reacting mixture	... 20.6	2.

Hence the absorption of energy by the solute = 20×2.85 ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

The number of quanta absorbed by the solute per sec. per sq. cm.

$$= \frac{20 \times 2.85 \times 10^{12}}{2.3} = 2.48 \times 10^{13}$$

In 70 minutes the change in the amount of iodine in light corresponds to a decrease of 3.9 c.c. of *N*/452-thiosulphate solution per 3 c.c. of the reacting mixture. In the dark the corresponding change is 3.59 c.c. of the same thiosulphate solution.

Therefore in pure light the decrease = $3.9 - 3.59 = 0.31$ c.c.

Hence, the rate of transformation of iodine molecules per sec. per sq. cm.

$$= \frac{0.31 \times 6.06 \times 10^{23} \times 3}{70 \times 60 \times 452 \times 1000 \times 2 \times 3} = 4.9 \times 10^{13}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{\text{No. of mols transformed}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed}} = \frac{4.9}{2.48} = 2.$$

Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride and Iodine.

N/5-Hydroxylamine hydrochloride = 5 c.c. *N*/100-Iodine = 10 c.c.
1.25*N*-Hydrochloric acid = 5 c.c.

Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in the dark. k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$ k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$ k_1	Temp. coeff. (dark).	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction.		Quantum yield.	
					$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$
30°	0.00535	0.00646	0.00692				3.5	2.85
30°	0.0186	0.0161	0.0146	2.54	2.25	2.28	5.4	3.8
40°	0.0333	0.0389	0.0382	2.45	2.20	2.23	8.2	5.6

Inversion of Cane Sugar.

20% Cane sugar = 15 c.c. *N*/20-Hydrochloric acid = 5 c.c.

The inversion was followed by using a polarimeter.

	k_1	k_1	k_1	k_{210}/k_{20}	k_{210}/k_{20}	k_{210}/k_{20}	145	112
30°	0.0000925	0.0001096	0.000101					
35°	0.000189	0.000212	0.000203	3.85	3.70	3.75	162	142
40°	0.000727	0.000813	0.000780				193	163

Oxalic Acid and Chlorine.

N/75-Chlorine = 10 c.c. 1.25*N*-Hydrochloric acid = 5 c.c. *N*/5-Oxalic acid = 5 c.c.

Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in the dark. k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$ k_1	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$ k_1	Temp. coeff. (dark).	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction.		Quantum yield.	
					$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}.$	$\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}.$
15°	0.0119	0.0149	0.0131				2.1×10^3	63
25°	0.0361	0.0426	0.0384	2.95	2.5	2.75	4.9×10^3	75
35°	0.102	0.120	0.111	2.90	2.42	2.72	8.6×10^3	94

This reaction was followed by titrating the change in the chlorine concentration with a standard thiosulphate solution.

Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 8500 \text{ \AA}$, k_1	Vel. of reaction in the dark. k_1	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction in $\lambda = 8500 \text{ \AA}$.	Quantum efficiency $\lambda = 8500 \text{ \AA}$.
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*Bleaching of M/7176-neocyanin.**

20°	0.00112	0.0000682		1.1	0.98
30°	0.00128	—		1.04	1.65
40°	0.00128	—			2.80

6.75N-Citric acid and N/44.4-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

24°	0.000413	0.000359	3.73	3.15	1.1
34°	0.00151	0.00134	3.65	2.90	3.2
44°	0.00534	0.00465			4.3

*Decomposition of M/80.8-sodium cobaltinitrite.**

20°	0.000730	0.000569	3.5	3.05	0.92
30°	0.00251	0.00202	3.04	2.84	1.3
40°	0.00754	0.00632			3.9

N/250-Ferric chloride and N/50-ammonium sulphocyanide, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.000179	0.0000017		2.72	2.5
30°	0.000471	—		2.61	3.9
40°	0.00123	—			5.6

N/10-Potassium oxalate and N/100-bromine, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.000819	0.00450	5.61	4.42	23
30°	0.0419	0.0256	5.2	4.30	51
40°	0.0203	0.133			72

* These reactions were followed by a Nutting's spectrophotometer.

Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$. k_1	Vel. of reaction in the dark. k_1	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction in $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$.	Quantum efficiency $\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$.
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*N/10-Ferrous sulphate (8 c.c.) + N/5.6-sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) and N/100-iodine (10 c.c.).**

	k_2	k_1	$\rightarrow$	k_2	k_{20}/k_{10}	k_{20}/k_{10}	
30°	0.000903	0.000377		0.000660			5.4
35°	0.00153	0.000675		0.00113	2.82	2.52	8.9
40°	0.00246	0.00112		0.00185			18.4

In presence of sulphuric acid the colour of ferric ion formed does not play any part in the optical measurements.

N/2.95-Potassium oxalate (10 c.c.) and N/11.36-iodine (10 c.c.).

	k_2	k_1	$\rightarrow$	k_2			
20°	0.00125	0.0000702		0.000050			2.1
30°	0.00767	0.0000487		0.00035	6.96	4.06	5.2
40°	0.0307	0.000386		0.0024	6.87	3.86	13.1

N/4.69-Sodium lactate (10 c.c.) and N/100-iodine (10 c.c.).

	k_1	k_1				
20°	0.000757	0.000720				1.8
30°	0.00187	0.00179			2.49	2.29
40°	0.00431	0.00414			2.81	2.13

N/2.42-Sodium tartrate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

	k_1	k_1				
20°	0.000895	0.000375				2.3
30°	0.000990	0.000848			2.51	2.47
40°	0.00246	0.00236			2.49	2.38

N/2.69-Sodium malonate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

	k_1	k_1				
20°	0.00251	0.00227				1.9
30°	0.00553	0.00503			2.22	2.08
40°	0.0120	0.0110			2.16	2.0

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Temperature.	Vel. of reaction in $\lambda=8500\text{\AA}$.	Vel. of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. in the dark.	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction in $\lambda=8500\text{\AA}$.	Quantum efficiency in $\lambda=8500\text{\AA}$.
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2/8N-Sodium nitrite (5 c.c.) + N/32-iodine (10 c.c.)
+ N/6.25-sodium acetate (5 c.c.).

	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$	k_1	→	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$		
30°	0.0147	0.00819		0.0090		36
40°	0.0876	0.00986		0.0241	2.70	52
50°	0.0835	0.0226		0.0537	2.61	79

N/5-Citric acid (10 c.c.) + N/50-KMnO₄ (5 c.c.) + N/69-MnSO₄ (5 c.c.).*

	k_1	k_1	k_{21}/k_{11}	k_{22}/k_{12}	
15°	0.00512	0.00479			1.02
25°	0.0148	0.0188			3.18
30°	0.0282	0.0219	2.92	2.56	4.25

In the above tables k_1 represents the unimolecular velocity coefficient and $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ the semimolecular coefficient calculated from the same experimental results carried on in the dark.

Discussion.

The experimental results show that radiations of wave-lengths 7304 $\text{\AA}$ and 8500 $\text{\AA}$ accelerate several photochemical reactions. From our measurements of light absorption with the help of a radiomicro-meter, it is evident that radiations of wave-lengths 7304 $\text{\AA}$ and 8500 $\text{\AA}$ are actually absorbed by the reacting system. The molecules of the reacting system are activated by the absorption of radiation and the activated molecules then react. From our experimental results we conclude that the halogen molecules need not be atomised in order to be active, because, in the reactions involving halogens which have been studied in this paper, it cannot be assumed that the halogen molecules have been atomised. The maximum wave-length necessary to atomise the halogens are as follows:—

Chlorine, 5400 $\text{\AA}$; bromine, 6230 $\text{\AA}$; iodine, 8360 $\text{\AA}$.

All these wave-lengths are shorter than the radiation of wave-length 8500 $\text{\AA}$ used in this investigation.

It is well known that in a system there are a few molecules, the energy of which is greater than the energy of the average molecules. When the incident radiation of wave-length $8500\text{\AA}$ falls on such an active molecule, the molecule is further activated by the absorption of this incident radiation and under favourable conditions the molecule may be atomised. This view might explain the atomisation of the halogen molecules by radiations longer than that calculated from the heat of dissociation. Unfortunately no case of atomisation of a molecule has been observed in the Raman-effect. Hence we are forced to the conclusion that an atomisation of a molecule in the Raman-phenomenon is not very probable and in all the photochemical reactions in radiations of wave-lengths $7304\text{\AA}$ and $8500\text{\AA}$ the halogen molecules are likely to be activated and not atomised.

We have emphasised in previous publications from these laboratories that Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence mostly fails in exothermal reactions. Many molecules react per quantum of energy absorbed. It seems likely that several molecules may be activated by the absorption of one quantum. Our experimental results recorded in this paper show that with several reactions Einstein's law is applicable when illuminated by radiations of wave-length $8500\text{\AA}$. It appears therefore that a quantum of small energy-content can activate one or two molecules and hence in radiations of longer wave-lengths the law of Einstein will be valid.

In previous publications we have emphasised that the wave-lengths obtained by the application Perrin-Lewis hypothesis may be looked upon as the threshold limit. No appreciable acceleration of the chemical change is likely to take place with radiations of longer wave-lengths than the threshold limit.

In the following table the threshold wave-lengths are calculated from their temperature coefficients.

Reacting mixture.	Temp. coeff. ("dark").	Wave-length.
Citric acid + chromic acid.	3.78	1.20
Decomposition of sodium cobaltinitrite.	3.50	1.3
Potassium oxalate + bromine.	5.6	0.94
Ferrous sulphate + iodine.	2.92	1.46
Potassium oxalate + iodine.	6.96	0.36
Citric acid + KMnO_4 + MnSO_4 .	2.92	1.46
Inversion of cane sugar.	3.85	1.19
Oxalic acid + chlorine.	2.95	1.47

It is evident that the above reactions should be accelerated by short infra-red radiations and actually they are accelerated by wave-lengths $7304\text{\AA}$ and $8500\text{\AA}$. It is also clear from our researches that all radiations of frequency greater than the threshold frequency calculated from the temperature coefficient are appreciably absorbed by the reacting systems and can accelerate the reactions investigated. These results support the view that radiation plays an important part in chemical reactions and our experiments strengthen the radiation hypothesis of chemical change.

Summary.

1. Sixteen reactions have been found to be accelerated by radiations of wave-length $8500\text{\AA}$, which lie in the infra-red region of the spectrum. Four reactions have also been studied in radiations of mean wave-length $7304\text{\AA}$.

2. A saturated solution of potassium dichromate placed in a cobalt-glass cell of one centimetre thickness cuts off all radiations shorter than $8000\text{\AA}$. This has been shown photographically.

The quantum efficiency of all these reactions increases with increase in temperature.

4. The temperature coefficients of all these reactions in radiations of wave-lengths $7304\text{\AA}$ and $8500\text{\AA}$ are less than those of the corresponding dark reactions.

5. Chemical changes can be accelerated by short infra-red radiations in such cases where the values theoretically obtained predict that possibility and that these radiations are appreciably absorbed by the reacting systems.

6. Our results support the view that radiation plays an important part in chemical reactions and that the halogen molecules are not atomised in these photochemical reactions.

